

NUMERICAL DESIGN OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS THROUGH MULTI-SCALE COMPUTER SIMULATION

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1.0 General Introduction

Design of ballistic composite materials is an expensive and tedious process. In most cases, design of truly “new” composite materials is done experimentally due to the expense involved in characterization of new composite materials required prior to conducting finite element (FE) simulation. The orthotropic nature of composite materials requires that the analyst conduct constitutive characterization in all 3 major axes as well as the 3 shear directions. Compounding the issue are both progressive damage and rate sensitivity considerations, requiring even more characterization testing with specialized equipment and additional hardware.

True numerical design of composite armor materials requires that the designer be able to reliably predict the mechanical properties of a composite with sufficient accuracy to estimate ballistic performance. To this end, under an effort funded by the Office of Naval Research, a program was initiated to develop and validate a multi-scale computer method to design armor composites numerically [1]. This 3 year effort first validated the concept through numerical constitutive characterization of a simple composite system, the HJ-1 (S2Glass/phenolic) composite armor system. In the next phase, a library of constitutive parameters for bare fibers and pure resin materials was generated. In the final phase, a composite was numerically designed and validated through ballistic testing.

2.0 Materials Characterization

While the method described here relies heavily on simulation, constitutive material models for the bare fiber and resin were required as inputs. Constitutive models for the laminating resin were developed

using characterization testing at strain rates from 0.0001 s^{-1} to $3,500 \text{ s}^{-1}$ using standard servo-hydraulic equipment and a compressive split-Hopkinson bar.

Characterization of the phenolic resin component of the HJ-1 composite system proved exceedingly difficult as water vapor (steam) generation during the curing process made containment of the phenolic difficult. Through the use of a 3 ton press and small mold, small sticks of pure phenolic resin were able to be cured. From these sticks, the specimens shown in Figure 1, were machined. Due to the brittleness of the phenolic resin, as well as impurities caused by the H₂O formation, a high scrap rate was seen.

Figure 1. Example specimens used for characterization of pure Lewcote Phenolic resin.

Characterization tests were conducted using the specimens in Figure 1 to develop a series of stress strain curves for the phenolic material, shown in Figure 2. The stress-strain response of the phenolic resin shows significant sensitivity to strain rate. The data were then tabulated for use in the

*MAT_RATE_DEPENDENT_PLASTICITY model in LS-Dyna.

Figure 2 Stress-strain response of Lewcott Phenolic Resin vs strain rate (compression).

The fiber constitutive material models were developed through a combination of testing and simulation. Molecular modeling was used to determine the transverse properties of the individual filaments (shear moduli, transverse modulus), and standard tensile testing was used to determine the axial properties. Tensile testing of the fibers required a custom designed split-Hopkinson bar fixture (Figure 3).

Figure 3 (a) The test specimen holder caps are set in the saddle and fibers are wound. (b) Specimen caps are put together and fixed using the saddle cap. (c) The specimen is attached to the tension SHB apparatus. (d) The saddle is removed just before specimen testing.

The custom designed fixture, due to its complex loading method, creates stress concentrations in the fiber bundle as it is wound around the pins. Also, an accurate measure of the gauge section length is difficult to determine. To this end, the data from the fiber fixture is used to provide a scaling factor to traditionally acquired data for the same fiber using a standard fiber strand test. Examples of the rate sensitivity curves for the fiber modulus and ultimate stress are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively. A comparison of the stress strain data collected using the fiber fixture, including both servo-hydraulic and Hopkinson-bar data is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 4. Example of Kevlar (tm) fiber modulus rate sensitivity.

Figure 5. Example of Kevlar (tm) fiber modulus rate sensitivity

Figure 6. Stress-strain data collected for Kevlar fiber using the fiber fixture.

While tensile testing was used to determine the axial properties of the fibers, the transverse and shear properties of the fibers were much more difficult to determine experimentally. To this end, molecular modeling was used to determine the constitutive parameters for the filaments simulated in the micro-scale model.

3.0 Multi-Scale Method

The multi-scale modeling method employs computer simulation at various scales to ultimately develop a constitutive continuum model for a single ply of a composite.

Initially, a simulation (micro-scale) is built of bare composite filaments in pure resin. An example of this unit cell model is shown in Figure 7. Bonding between the pure resin and fiber materials can be handled through tying of the boundary nodes, allowing debonding only at the point of resin failure, or thorough tied contact with a programmed failure stress. The unit cell is deformed in series of numerical characterization experiments to determine the orthotropic material properties of the unit cell through the use of various constraints, and programmed deformations.

Figure 7 Example of micro-scale unit cell model.

Within the micro-scale unit cell model, variables such as fiber content, resin materials, fiber pullout stress, and angle of twist (requiring a significantly larger simulation than shown in Figure 7) can be investigated.

The results of the micro-scale simulations are then processed to create a constitutive model for the resin impregnated fiber bundle (IFB). This constitutive model provides a continuum approximation for the IFB simulated in the micro-scale simulation.

This data is then used in one of two ways. In the case of a uni-directional (UD) composite, the data can be used directly to simulate a UD ply in the intended composite material design. In the case of a woven composite, the data is used to populate the material model for the fiber rich, IFB portions of the meso scale model, green and yellow materials in Figure 8. The red materials in the example model shown in Figure 8 are again modeled as pure resin. The simulation is then exercised similarly to the micro-scale simulation to determine an orthotropic set of material properties for the single woven ply. These data can then be used to simulate the final woven composite in any number of applications.

Figure 8 Example of meso-scale model.

4.0 HJ-1 Validation

The simulation method was first validated in 2009 under this effort using the HJ-1 composite system. This composite was chosen for multiple reasons. First, under a different effort, Battelle had generated a constitutive model for HJ-1 using traditional mechanical testing, providing a basis for validation. Second, because the fibers in the HJ-1 composite system are S2-Glass, the fibers could be assumed to be isotropic, significantly simplifying the micro-scale simulations.

Micro-scale simulations were run using the constitutive data presented in Table 1 and Table 2, below. Delamination between the explicitly modeled filaments and the pure resin regions in the unit cell model was handled through tiebreak contact. It was assumed that delamination occurred at the onset of plastic deformation within the resin. Therefore, the delamination stress within the tiebreak contact was set to the yield stress of the resin. Further, based on the average HJ-1 density and simple geometric calculations estimating the fiber bundle dimensions, a fiber content of 75% was assumed for the micro-scale unit cell model.

Table 1. Rate dependent plasticity data for Lewcott phenolic resin.

Density (gm/mm ³)	Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Yield Stress (MPa)	Tangent Modulus (MPa)
1.19E-03	2.00E-04	1.02	55	94
	1	1.64	95	587
	1.94E+03	2.08	150	755
	4.12E+03	3.02	167	1264
	1.96E+04	21.2	197	3

Table 2. Isotropic constitutive data used for S2-Glass filament simulation.

Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Density (gm/mm ³)	Poisson's Ratio	Failure Stress (GPa)	Fiber Dia (μm)
85.5	2.49E-03	0.2	2.5	9.144

The micro-scale unit cell model was exercised to develop an orthotropic material model for the phenolic resin impregnated S2-Glass fiber bundle (IFB) in the HJ-1 composite. The constitutive model generated (*MAT_162) is presented below in Table 3. As expected, the axial properties of the fiber bundle are dominated by the S2-Glass properties. The transverse directions are more complicated. The high through-thickness modulus of the fiber drives the transverse modulus, while the high strength of the fiber is only seen in the transverse compressive failure stress. The shear properties of the IFB show interesting properties as well, the two longitudinal shear moduli appear to be dominated by the high strength and rigidity of the fiber, while the transverse shear mode is dominated by the resin properties and bond strength between the resin and fiber.

Table 3. Orthotropic characterization parameters for the S2-Glass / Phenolic IFB (75% S2-Glass).

Rho (gm/mm ³)	Ea (GPa)	Eb (GPa)	Ec (GPa)
2.29E-03	70.8	30.9	30.9
PRba	PRca	PRcb	
0.075	0.075	0.38	
Gab (GPa)	Gbc (GPa)	Gca (GPa)	
14.4	2.3	14.4	
SaT (MPa)	SaC (MPa)	SbT (MPa)	SbC (MPa)
1875	1875	400	2040
Sab (MPa)	Sbc (MPa)	Sca (MPa)	
1200	108	1200	
ScT (MPa)	SfC (MPa)	SfS (MPa)	
400	2040	N/A	

The data from the micro scale model was then used to populate the IFB portions of the meso-scale model. The resin rich portions of this model were populated with data from Table 1. The specific geometry of the woven fabric was created using measurements of HJ-1 composite panels at Battelle. The interaction between different fiber bundles, as well as between the fiber bundles and the resin rich regions is handled using the *MAT_162 internal delamination routines.

The IFB element geometry was setup such that the axial fiber direction did not need to be defined explicitly, in other words, material direction was defined by the element connectivity. While multiple methods were investigated for defining the material directions, the most robust and simple one was to define each IFB as a separate part with element connectivity, such that the fiber direction need not be defined within the material model.

Much like the micro-scale model, the meso-scale model was exercised to develop a series of stress strain relations so that a constitutive material model could be generated for a single ply of HJ-1. The constitutive model that was developed, and its comparison with experimental data is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Final numerical characterization results for the HJ-1 composite system with comparisons to actual experimental data.

HJ-1	Rho (gm/mm ³)	Ea (GPa)	Eb (GPa)	Ec (GPa)
Numerical	1.94E-03	30.6	30.6	5.82
Experimental	1.90E-03	32.4	32.4	6.1
	PRba	PRca	PRcb	
Numerical	0.1	0.1	0.1	
Experimental	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Gab (GPa)	Gbc (GPa)	Gca (GPa)	
Numerical	5.39	0.453	0.453	
Experimental	7.4	0.2	0.2	
	SaT (MPa)	SaC (MPa)	SbT (MPa)	SbC (MPa)
Numerical	562.5	300	562.5	300
Experimental	500	N/A	500	N/A
	Sab (MPa)	Sbc (MPa)	Sca (MPa)	
Numerical	147	41.7	41.7	
Experimental	40.8	26.2	26.2	
	ScT (MPa)	SFC (MPa)	SFS (MPa)	
Numerical	250	1110	325	
Experimental	N/A	1020	200	

As shown in the table, the multi-scale computer simulation excelled in predicting the in-plane properties of the composite. The three principal moduli (A, B, C) were predicted with a great degree of accuracy. The tensile failure stresses for the primary in plane directions were also predicted well. The shear modulus prediction appears to provide a “ballpark” prediction of the shear parameters. Accuracy could be added to the shear predictions through incorporation of fiber pullout data, which would provide a much better base point for calculation of the delamination stresses in the meso-scale model.

6.0 Material Data Library

In the next phase of the effort, constitutive data for a wide variety of fibers and resins was collected. The team collected constitutive data for Ultra-High

Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE), Kevlar, PBO (As Spun or (AS)), S2-Glass, and Featherlight S2-Glass. The team also collected constitutive data on multiple epoxy as well as thermoplastic and phenolic resins.

The experimental constitutive data for the resin materials was fit to appropriate material models. All of the resins, with the exception of the thermoplastic, fit the *RATE_DEPENDENT_PLASTICITY model quite well. The thermoplastic resin material was better suited to a rubber model.

The experimental data for the fibers, as it only included the axial data, was augmented by the inclusion of molecular modeling to determine the transverse and shear properties of the filaments, allowing orthotropic treatment of the filaments in the micro-scale models.

7.0 Ballistic Validation

The final phase of the effort was to validate the multi-scale simulation method through the design of a ballistic composite panel. For the effort, two PBO / Epoxy panels were designed and validated; woven and UD architectures were chosen. The simulations were compared to the experimental data through impact-residual velocity and pyramid half-base/height measurement. The 17 grain right circular cylinder (RCC) fragment simulating projectile (FSP) was used for testing.

The initial design effort focused on development of a unidirectional PBO composite. It was intended that two iterations of design / simulate / test would be completed to create an optimized UD PBO composite. Delays in manufacturing the UD PBO tapes required prevented that from being feasible, and a replacements material was sought for the first iteration. Therefore, for the first test iteration, woven PBO fabric that Battelle had in stock was used to press the first set of panels for validation.

While the panels were being prepared, the multi-scale simulation method was exercised to determine the mechanical properties of a single ply of woven PBO / Epoxy composite, the results are presented in Table 5. These parameters were then used to predict ballistic performance of the composite. Similarly to

the HJ-1 simulations, measurements of the fabric, as well as its predicted compressibility, were used to generate the finite element (FE) geometry of the woven PBO fabric.

Table 5. Simulation parameters used to simulate the woven PBO / Epoxy composite.

Rho (gm/mm³)	Ea (GPa)	Eb (GPa)	Ec (GPa)
1.38E-03	31.5	31.5	4.58
Prba	Prca	PRcb	
0.3	0.05	0.05	
Gab (GPa)	Gbc (GPa)	Gca (GPa)	
0.71	0.909	0.909	
SaT (MPa)	SaC (MPa)	SbT (MPa)	SbC (MPa)
900	300	900	300
Sab (MPa)	Sbc (MPa)	Sca (MPa)	
14.9	12	12	
ScT (MPa)	SFC (MPa)	SFS (MPa)	
60.2	1000	N/A	

Shown in Figure 9, is that the simulations were able to not only predict the penetration velocity of the 17 grain projectile, but the general slope of the impact velocity – residual velocity curve was also predicted.

Figure 9. Impact vs residual velocity plot for the woven PBO / Epoxy composite (testing courtesy of Southwest Research Institute (SwRI)).

The pyramid half base predictions are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11. As the images show, the simulations are able to predict the experimental results to within 2mm of deformation through the entire data collection. The pyramid half base comparison shows that the constitutive model (Table 5) for the woven ply is able to adequately represent the axial sound speed of the ply. The pyramid height comparison shows that the constitutive model is adequately capturing the through-thickness sound speed of the composite.

Figure 10. Pyramid half base measurements and simulation data for the woven PBO / Epoxy composite (testing courtesy of SwRI).

Figure 11. Pyramid height measurements and simulation data for the woven PBO / Epoxy composite (testing courtesy of SwRI).

Upon completion of the woven PBO / epoxy composite test series, work began on the UD PBO / epoxy composite panels. Once the UD PBO tape was received, the research team began preparation of the test panels. When preparation was complete, the fiber content of the panels was computed, allowing simulations to begin. However, due the large denier of the yarns in the UD tape, the envisioned fiber content of 75 to 80% (by volume) could not be realized. The fiber content (by volume) of the final UD panels was approximately 60%.

As with the woven PBO composite, multi-scale simulations were used to determine the mechanical properties of the UD composite. The parameters developed for the single UD plies are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Parameters used to simulate the UD PBO / Epoxy composite (60% PBO by volume).

Rho (gm/mm ³)	Ea (GPa)	Eb (GPa)	Ec (GPa)
1.38E-03	88.9	2.22	2.22
PRba	PRca	PRcb	
0.001	0.001	0.3	
Gab (GPa)	Gbc (GPa)	Gca (GPa)	
0.375	0.466	0.375	
SaT (MPa)	SaC (MPa)	SbT (MPa)	SbC (MPa)
2630	500	81	1000
Sab (MPa)	Sbc (MPa)	Sca (MPa)	
27.6	46.6	27.6	
ScT (MPa)	SFC (MPa)	SFS (MPa)	
81	1000	N/A	

Figure 12, shows that the simulations were able to predict both the penetration velocity of the 17 grain RCC FSP as well as the slope of the impact vs residual velocity curve. The pyramid half base and pyramid height predictions, presented in Figure 13 and Figure 14, respectively, show some flaws in the simulations. The Pyramid half base comparison makes apparent that the simulation diverges further from the actual result as the test goes on. This shows that the constitutive model (Table 6) is underestimating the longitudinal sound speed in the UD plies. This is not surprising, as the code estimates the sound speed as a function of modulus and density, resulting in an effective sound speed reduction of 40%.

Figure 12. Impact vs residual velocity plot for the UD PBO / Epoxy composite (testing courtesy of SwRI).

Figure 13. Pyramid half base measurements and simulation data for the UD PBO / Epoxy composite (testing courtesy of SwRI).

Figure 14. Pyramid height measurements and simulation data for the UD PBO / Epoxy composite (testing courtesy of SwRI).

8.0 Discussion

The use of multi-scale computer simulation has been shown here to provide constitutive predictions for composite materials. Through validation in both mechanical and ballistic testing it has been shown that composite performance can be adequately predicted. It was not the intent of this effort to develop a method to eliminate the need for constitutive testing of composite materials however. Rather, the intent of this effort was to develop a tool that can be used to refine composite materials by tuning parameters including modulus, strength, delamination, etc before conducting expensive characterization testing. The use of this type of analysis has vast applications in structural composite analysis as well as ballistic composite analysis.

9.0 References

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